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WP1: Code optimization & scaling

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Executive Summary

This document describes the contents of the fourth project release (second in BioExcel-2), of software developed for the core applications in BioExcel. In addition to describing the final releases in BioExcel-2 for the core applications, this document also presents what has been achieved in terms of features and performance for the codes over the entire project timeframe.

To provide reference versions of all codes used in the project (e.g. to integrate them in BioExcel workflows and use by other BioExcel teams), the Work Package also makes these formal code releases. This also comes with records describing the current status of the software that results from the planning, development, documentation, and testing processes.

The release itself takes the form of a package of Open Source licensed source code with accompanying documentation, tests, benchmarks, and benchmark reports and can be downloaded from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6761700> or from the BioExcel webpage at <http://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories>. All codes (apart from CP2K whose core development team is external to BioExcel) have now timed the BioExcel release to be in sync with the individual product releases, so there is less confusion for the users, as well as less maintenance and documentation overhead for the developers.

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1 Introduction

To deliver impact to users, BioExcel makes official releases of the codes with new features as well as performance improvements. The final releases for the BioExcel-2 project are described in this deliverable. The main codes in the CoE have been selected on a wide user base in the EU as well as frequent use on EuroHPC/PRACE resources. All code developed in the CoE is open source and development can be tracked through the code repositories of the different codes.

Previously, most of the codes provided separate project releases, to be used by other parts of the project, such as the workflows in WP2. But as this can lead to confusion for users and to more testing and maintenance work for developers, we have decided to synchronize the major releases of all codes with the project releases.

The codes currently supported are selected based on their usage to study proteins, lipids, RNA, DNA, energy processes in cells, and in particular drug design applications requiring large-scale docking and free energy calculation:

- **GROMACS** is a high-performance task-parallel molecular dynamics software simulation and analysis suite. GROMACS is one of the most widely used biomolecular simulation codes in the world (accounting for some 5% of worldwide HPC time), and in particular in Europe, where it is one of the PRACE benchmark codes. The BioExcel work is focused on scaling and performance improvements, porting all acceleration to new Exascale hardware, as well as implementing modern techniques for modularization, documentation, code review and QA testing.
- **PMX** is a code for automatically preparing molecular topologies for advanced free energy calculations, which is a particularly important target for using massive amounts of molecular simulations both in academia and industry. This is a key factor in enabling researchers to automatically scan through and calculate free energy of binding for tens of thousands of compounds using MD tools such as GROMACS.
- **HADDOCK** is an implementation of bio-molecular docking based on a wide range of biochemical information. This code has a very different usage profile, and it has been selected because of the importance of improving support for high-throughput life science calculations. HADDOCK is a key component of the many workflows developed in BioExcel. Its main mode of use is via its web portal.
- **CP2K** is a high-performance quantum chemistry application widely used in materials science, solid state physics and computational chemistry, and is a PRACE benchmark code. BioExcel has developed an interface that enables hybrid QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems by coupling GROMACS to CP2K, thereby leveraging the latter's use of large-scale HPC resources for QM calculations and is improving CP2K's QM/MM performance and scaling as part of a development roadmap to ready the coupled applications to efficiently exploit exascale resources. This work is underpinned by the creation and ongoing expansion of a public

biomolecular QM/MM benchmark suite, which will also aid future CP2K development outside of BioExcel through its integration - along with BioExcel-developed code - into the canonical CP2K codebase, and which will contribute to PRACE benchmarking work where it is also planned to be used.

In addition to software development focused directly on the applications themselves, another important part of the usability improvements in BioExcel comes from integrating them into workflows as presented in work package 2.

During the project the connections between the applications have become stronger. An obvious example is QM/MM where a QM and MM code need to be linked together, CP2K and GROMACS in this case. Here a new interface was developed, based on the MDModule framework in GROMACS. On the one hand the two applications need to be adapted to each other's needs. On the other hand, the MDModule interface is a general API that can also be used to couple other QM code to GROMACS and even other special “force-provider” libraries, if the need for that arises. Also the development of PMX and GROMACS has become more connected, with, for example, the implementation of the new soft-core functional form used by PMX into GROMACS.

User-driven development has become a strong focus during BioExcel-2. Although one cannot let users decide independently over the direction of the different codes, it is clear that the codes are there to serve the needs of current as well as future users. User needs have been gathered in questionnaires sent out to users and handed out during workshops and school, from interactions on forums and through direct requests on issue trackers. But the most useful and detailed information can be gathered through direct physical interactions with users at physical events.

In this document we list features and performance improvements in response to user requests for all codes. In particular the GROMACS/CP2K QM/MM development has been user driven. As this was a new project that began at the start of BioExcel-2, user needs were crucial for deciding on development directions. Not so much for features, as those are rather straightforward from the QM side and the QM/MM interface in GROMACS gives access to nearly all GROMACS features, including the very relevant enhanced sampling with e.g. the accelerated weight histogram (AWH) method. Relevant use cases have been critical for focusing the efforts on optimising the performance of QM/MM. Performance analysis revealed several bottlenecks on the QM side, which have been effectively addressed in the final project release. Our experience supporting new users of the QM/MM interface revealed that installation often proved problematic. We therefore collaborated with the CP2K core development team, who in response to our request modified CP2K to produce link line information that could automatically be picked up by GROMACS when building it with the QM/MM interface.

BioExcel is committed to business-friendly open-source licensing for all code developed in the project, but to generate impact for the most widely used

application codes we also need to ensure the code can be used with existing code bases and their licences. This is handled by making all BioExcel code available as independent libraries or scripts, which can easily be adapted to other codes too when more liberal licences are available.

The licenses used in BioExcel are the Lesser GNU General Public License ([LGPL](#)) v2.1 or later (GROMACS), [LGPL v3](#) (pmx) and the [Apache License 2.0](#) (HADDOCK scripts, as well as WP2 workflows), [BSD 2-Clause](#) (CP2K benchmark script), [Creative Commons Zero \(CC0\)](#) (CP2K benchmark data). These are all [OSI-approved](#) and well-recognized Open Source licenses that grant the right to run the code for any purpose, to link it into closed commercial applications, as well as to modify and/or redistribute the code. The licenses differ mainly in details such as restrictions on derived works (LGPL is a [Copyleft](#) license, while Apache 2.0 and BSD 2-Clause are [Permissive licenses](#)) or protections against software patent infringements (included in Apache License 2.0 and LGPL 3). GROMACS source code is licensed for “2.1 or later” versions of LGPL, meaning it can be upgraded to LGPL 3 for pmx compatibility. All licences are compatible with [GPL 3](#) linking, needed by the [GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM interface](#).

2 GROMACS

[GROMACS](#) is one of the main codes for molecular simulations and represents a large part of the BioExcel-2 development in the realm of high level parallelization and accelerator support for pre-exascale machines and simulation setups. The development effort provided by BioExcel-2 made it possible for the GROMACS team to continue the efforts on increasing simulation performance and reducing time to solution for systems of scientific interest, as well as adding new features based on user interactions.

2.1 Software achievements in GROMACS over the course of BioExcel-2

Continuing from the work started over the course of BioExcel-1, the GROMACS project made sure to keep the regular release schedule, with one major release and several patch releases each year (see the information in Figure 1 for the course of 2021). To further enable reliable software distribution channels and ensure that users can refer to exact versions used for their simulations, all [releases](#) starting from the 2019 major release have also been assigned DOIs for improved referencing and verification. The latest release of GROMACS has been the 2022.1 patch release (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451564>), containing bug fixes and usability enhancements for the 2022 release series. This allows the team to separate the work on new feature development in the main branch from purely maintenance and stability related tasks for the currently released versions.

Figure 1: Overview of GROMACS releases during the course of BioExcel-2.

As the core GROMACS development team at KTH continues to be supported by BioExcel-2, the focus has continued to be on the integration of features developed as part of the BioExcel-2 project, as well as the distribution of new releases through BioExcel related channels on the User Forum (gromacs.bioexcel.eu) and other streams.

The planned second patch release of the 2022 series, as well as the final maintenance release of 2021 are coinciding with the final releases of the BioExcel-2 project. This means that users relying on the versions released under the umbrella of BioExcel-2 will have access to a final, very stable branch version, as well as a stable branch version that has already undergone two rounds of extensive bug fixing. In addition to this, nightly builds of the main branch are always available to use new, experimental features, and can be relied on to have passed integration and regression testing before being accepted there. See deliverable *D1.1 – Specification of software engineering and QA* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6007882>) for details on the GROMACS release policy.

As has been the case since the first BioExcel supported release, each release comes with a full set of release notes, containing information about new features, useability and performance improvements, and bug fixes. All those entries are also linked to the relevant issues in our issue tracking system on GitLab (<https://gitlab.com/gromacs/gromacs/-/issues>), which allows users to quickly verify that those issues that might be affecting them are indeed resolved in a new version or not.

New features appearing in the 2019 and 2020 releases have been mentioned in Deliverable 1.4 ([10.5281/zenodo.4916009](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916009)) and the final project report for

BioExcel-1 ([10.5281/zenodo.1474181](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1474181)). For the 2021 and 2022 series, a selection of new features relevant to BioExcel-2 are listed below:

- The accelerated weight histogram method can now be used to perform alchemical transformations, providing simpler and more easily parallelizable free energy calculations
- A multiple time stepping algorithm has been integrated
- Multiple particle-mesh Ewald grids can be offloaded to GPUs, allowing support for fully GPU-accelerated free energy calculations
- Full support for arm *SVE* SIMD instructions
- Support for running QM/MM calculations with CP2K
- Arbitrary mathematical transformation of pull reaction coordinates
- New soft-core potentials for improved stability of free energy calculations
- GPU direct communication with CUDA aware MPI
- SIMD support for nonbonded free energy kernels, accelerates the kernel by a factor of 3 and simulations by up to a factor 2.5
- Update and constraints can run on a GPU, this provides a significant speedup on machines with fast GPUs
- Speed up for preprocessing tool `gmx grompp`

From this (non-exhaustive) list, BioExcel-2 funded the majority of the simulation feature development, as well as all the integration work to ensure new features work well together with the existing code base. In addition to this, all work related to release management, code stability and testing, and coverage in CI was fully supported by BioExcel-2.

2.2 Highlights

One major acceleration feature integrated during the course of BioExcel-2 has been offloading the complete simulation loop to Nvidia GPU devices, as well as allowing direct communication between accelerator devices. These features have been developed in close collaboration with engineers from Nvidia, to ensure optimal performance on modern hardware. One example of the performance enhancements is shown in Figure 2. Please note that some of the direct GPU communication features are still not enabled by default, as they require more extensive testing to ensure proper function with all GROMACS features.

For free-energy calculations, which are an important class of calculations in both academia and pharmaceutical industry, the porting of the free energy kernels to use *single-instruction multiple-data* (SIMD) has had a major impact on performance. This is the only class of calculation where users, both from industry and academia, have been requesting better performance of GROMACS. The main issue was when running on machines with CPUs+GPUs, as these kernels run on the CPU and therefore can become a bottleneck leading to high idle times on GPUs. Adding SIMD made the kernels a factor 3 faster. This makes free-energy simulations a factor 2.5 faster when a fast GPU is combined with a slow CPU. This provides massive performance improvements for studies like drug binding, which can consume a large amount of compute resources. As highlighted in *D2.6 – Integration of BioExcel software framework with standards and international initiatives* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5824544>) SIMD and CUDA GPU support variations across hardware has [impacted binary packaging of GROMACS](#),

so we also developed a SIMD-capability detector that the BioExcel Docker and Conda images use to dispatch to the corresponding optimised GROMACS compiled binary at runtime.

On the methods side, one major new feature has been the implementation of [transformation pull coordinates](#), allowing users to pull molecules according to arbitrary, user-defined mathematical expressions. This has been a highly requested feature and has been one of the main reasons for users looking at other software packages when wanting to perform biasing simulations with more complex reaction coordinates.

Figure 2: Showcase of new GROMACS features of free-energy profiles of transfer of ammonia through four mutants of aquaporin. The free-energy was calculated using the Accelerated weight histogram method, which has been extended with more flexible sharing of biases. In this showcase up to 32 walkers, which are copies of the system, share a bias, exchanging information frequently. Together with the new GPU direct communication scheme, this enables a single MPU job to use 512 Nvidia V100 GPUs to solve this problem in 6 hours, compared to 192 hours without AWH and GPU parallelization.

2.3 Strategies for usage of extreme-scale resources with GROMACS

The GROMACS development team has continued its two-fold approach in improving scaling and performance for the expected exa-scale systems of the coming future. While significant effort is being invested to ensure that single simulations can use available hardware as much as possible, and can take advantage of new node designs with multiple accelerator devices (fat nodes), the team is still pursuing the field of ensemble parallelism as well. With the recent releases, the [gmxapi Python interface](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009835) [https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009835] and job scheduler have become more and more robust, to ensure users can easily set up and run large ensemble simulations with tools available in every GROMACS version. In addition to this, the AWH method has been extended to support more simulation setups and use cases, making it possible to use the inherent parallelism of its implementation to reduce the time to solution for a problem by distributing it to more simulations instances. The team will continue this work, and will also focus on providing more stable

APIs both on the Python and C++ levels to run large numbers of simulations efficiently.

3 PMX

[pmx](#) is a software package that allows for the setup and subsequent analysis of alchemical free energy calculations. pmx supports amino acid and nucleic acid mutations as well as arbitrary ligand modifications. In addition to supporting the structure and topology preparation for the subsequent simulations, pmx aims to provide a full free energy calculation workflow. The modular nature of the workflow elements allows for a flexible incorporation of GROMACS/pmx into academic and industrial pipelines.

3.1 pmx development in the course of BioExcel-2

The original pmx implementation was based on the Python 2 programming language, for which support by Python developers ended in 2020. It was therefore one of the major goals for the pmx code development to transition all of the classes, modules and scripts to Python 3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671368>). This transition puts the further pmx development on a track of incorporating novel features and enhancing scalability.

In the period of BioExcel-1 we have started developing pmx capabilities to deal with the relative *protein-ligand binding free energy* (RBFE) calculations. In BioExcel-2 we further enhanced the already available features and automated a workflow for efficiently running such calculations at large scale. Also, we further embarked on a challenge to support a conceptually different *absolute binding free energy* (ABFE) setup. The newly added modules allow for automation of the protein-ligand restraints that are necessary for ABFE setup.

Another commonly encountered challenge when performing alchemical free energy calculations is the proper treatment of annihilation/creation of a charge in the simulation box. We have thoroughly explored the magnitude of potential artefacts that could originate due to uncompensated charges in the system. We have now also implemented an automated single-system-double-box setup allowing us to circumvent this issue by preparing the simulation box such that it remains neutral during the complete alchemical transformation.

In addition, a number of new features have been implemented to facilitate analysis of the results obtained from non-equilibrium alchemical calculations. The pmx analysis module is now operating faster, allows input data slicing, enables block-based and bootstrapped uncertainty estimation and provides a convergence measure for the Bennett Acceptance ratio estimator.

As the pmx-enabled free energy calculations rely on GROMACS molecular dynamics engine for sampling the phase space of biomolecules, we actively participate in GROMACS development. In the course of BioExcel-2 we have implemented an alternative soft-core function into GROMACS that allows avoiding artifacts in the non-equilibrium free energy calculations that are frequently carried out with pmx. In a continued collaboration with the GROMACS team we

have enhanced the efficiency and robustness of the free energy calculations in GROMACS.

3.2 Developments for COVID-19 research

At the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, we aimed to contribute to the scientific investigations in understanding the thermodynamics of SARS-Cov2 interactions with the human ACE2 receptor and antibodies. To allow for an efficient evaluation of amino acid mutation effects on the protein-protein interactions, we have devised a multi-level screening strategy.

Firstly, an interface for a Rosetta-based rapid mutational screening was implemented into pmx. This allowed for a quick and computationally inexpensive identification of potential mutational hot-spots in ACE2 receptor or antibodies interacting with the SARS-Cov2 spike protein.

In the second step of the workflow, the promising mutation candidates were selected for an alchemical calculation of binding affinity changes. Such a workflow combines the fast approximate free energy estimation with the more accurate, yet computationally demanding molecular dynamics simulations to make predictions about the mutation induced protein-protein binding free energy differences. See deliverable *D6.3 – High Performance Computing in support of COVID-19 Research* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840055>) and the publication (<https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.1622>) for details.

3.3 Scaling in the HPC and Cloud environment

Alchemical free energy calculations readily provide highly accurate estimation of protein-ligand binding affinity changes. However, for the methods to be routinely applicable in the prospective drug discovery projects, a sufficient throughput must be ensured. In the course of BioExcel-2 we have constructed free energy calculation workflows (Figure 3) for the use on HPC, as well as for a cloud-based infrastructure: for details see publications (<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.1c01445> and <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.2c00044>). The application of these workflows in large scale protein-ligand binding affinity prediction is described in more detail in WP3 deliverable 3.6 Use Case 5. These developments enable the adoption of the GROMACS/pmx free energy calculation framework for academic and industrial applications requiring high accuracy and throughput.

Figure 3: GROMACS/pmx based protein-ligand binding free energy calculation schemes for HPC (left) and Cloud infrastructure (right).

4 HADDOCK

The development of [HADDOCK](#) has been divided into two branches: the 2.x and 3 series, each with a different roadmap. The HADDOCK 2.x will stay as the main production version for the time being. HADDOCK2.x is accessible either as the long-running web service (wenmr.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4) or as command line local installation. The implementation of user-requested features, as well as user support for the 2.x series, shall continue via the support channels - ask.bioexcel.eu - and via e-mail communication (haddock.support@gmail.com).

The 3 series represents a complete rewrite of the HADDOCK machinery into independent modules that can be freely combined to form project-specific modelling pipelines. It has also been designed with the idea of easily allowing the integration of third-party tools and addition of new modules. As such it offers much more flexibility to users.

4.1 HADDOCK2.x achievements during the course of BioExcel-2

During the course of the project, several features were introduced into HADDOCK2.4, either to expand the scientific capabilities of the code and/or upon user requests. Best coding practices were incorporated into the development workflow.

Versioning

Previous HADDOCK versions followed an untagged rolling release scheme. Under BioExcel we have implemented a variation of [semantic versioning](#) in the format of *2.X.YEAR-MONTH* to facilitate reproducibility and user support. New versions are released once a sufficient number of new features have been accumulated in the code base.

GRID/HTC optimization and code Scalability

HADDOCK has three possible execution methods, 1) thread, 2) high throughput computing (HTC) using a local batch system (e.g. on a local cluster) and 3) HTC mode making use of the EGI/EOSC distributed grid resources via the EGI

Workload Manager. These are handled directly by the source code (not via the web application).

To accommodate its high usage (>28,900 users with >135,800 jobs submitted since May 2019) the HADDOCK2.4 source code has been optimized to make the best use of the computing resources, but also to lower the execution load on the server. This allowed HADDOCK to process concurrently a larger number of runs, which was key to responding to the increased service demand as a result of COVID19.

Changelog

Since the beginning of BioExcel-2, the following new features and bug fixes have been added to HADDOCK, listed below as a condensed list:

- Added support for several glycans and glycosylated proteins
- Added glycan-specific scoring scripts
- Added support for various modified nucleic acids and amino acid
- Some bug fixes for clustering during refinement runs
- Implemented error checks for solvated docking and waterdock
- Bug fixes related to the restrain of ions in space
- Improvements, optimizations and bug fixes to the scheduler routines (HTC and GRID)
- Fixed issues with the run diagnostics
- Corrected issue with automatic histidine protonation state
- Added automatic definition of restraints to maintain ions in their coordination sphere and/or restrained in space
- Modified analysis scripts to work with a single ligand molecule

Toolbox

Over the lifetime of HADDOCK, several scripts and tools were developed by students, PhD candidates, postdocs and the user community. These represent useful additions to the analysis or preparation of input for HADDOCK simulations and were thus made public in BioExcel-1 ([D1.2 – First project release of all pilot applications, Bioexcel-1](#)). During the course of BioExcel-2, these tools have been continuously improved and new scripts have been added, all of which are freely available from github.com/haddock/haddock-tools. Moreover, pdb-tools is under active development at github.com/haddock/pdb-tools and is now also available as a web service; wenmr.science.uu.nl/pdbtools.

Scaling in HPC environment

In the topic of benchmarking and scaling, a novel machinery for running HADDOCK on HPC systems has been developed at github.com/haddock/haddock-pilot. This pilot was used to demonstrate HADDOCK's strong scaling in the [BioExcel CoE Scalability Report of Flagship codes](#) (Figure 4), measuring its scalability in delivering in the shortest time possible models of all predicted interactions for a given dataset. Further to facilitate HADDOCK's usage in large scale studies a new benchmarking tool was also introduced in an effort to streamline the process github.com/haddock/benchmark-tools.

Figure 4: HADDOCK scaling performance on a dataset of 100 biomolecular complexes of similar size, running the full workflow, sampling 10 000 models during the rigid body sampling stage and refining 200 of the best ones - for each complex.

4.2 HADDOCKv3 development during BioExcel-2

[HADDOCKv3](#) went from a prototype to a stable near-to-production version during BioExcel-2. Our efforts were spearheaded by increasing challenges in modelling and analysing complex macromolecular systems that require the ability to define custom workflows, something for which HADDOCK2.x was not designed. The new HADDOCKv3 workflow manager and

command line interfaces are fully built in Python 3.

In particular, we split the static HADDOCK2.x computational workflow into several individualised modules and implemented new analysis and clustering modules. These modules (fifteen to date) are organized into five categories: topology creation, sampling, refinement, scoring, and analysis. They can be natively implemented based on modularised HADDOCK code or wrap around third-party software that provide different strategies for the same conceptual process, such as *gdock* and *lightdock*, two third-party software that provide an alternative for rigid-body sampling.

Based on these modules, sixteen different modelling workflows are provided covering different applications examples for the modelling of e.g. antibody-antigen, protein-ligand and protein-DNA complexes, illustrating different execution modes (multiprocessing, HPC via a batch system or MPI). Those workflows are defined in custom configuration files following a syntax similar to TOML that allows repeated header names and internal types conversion which

further facilitates user interaction with HADDOCKv3. All the user-definable parameters for each module and their documentation resources are defined in convenient YAML files. In the custom workflow configuration files users only need to define non-default parameters, which also greatly simplify those files. HADDOCKv3, as well as external projects building upon ours, can read these YAML files directly, e.g. to validate the user workflow configuration files or build a graphical interface for a workflow builder and the associated parameters, thus avoiding duplication of efforts.

Further, we improved the user experience and HADDOCKv3 versatility by adding functionalities to the command-line interfaces. For example, to continue or expand runs and thoroughly validate input parameters before undergoing heavy calculations.

Following the European Open-Science requirements and F.A.I.R. principles, the HADDOCKv3 repository and source code is organised, traceable and open. We have implemented a series of advanced measures to ensure a healthy development environment as the project size and contributors scales up. HADDOCK v3 code and development brainstorming are, as much as possible, openly hosted on GitHub (github.com/haddock/haddock3), and organised under “Code”, “Issues”, “Pull Requests”, and “Projects” tabs. Users are however encouraged to register at <https://www.bonvinlab.org/software/haddock3> so that we can have a better overview of the user community and provide better support.

Therefore, collaborators, software developers and users can openly participate and learn from the HADDOCKv3 developing process. Furthermore, we have implemented extensive and robust continuous integration workflows that operate on GitHub actions to execute unit tests automatically, correct code style, test package build, bump the version number (according to SemVer2.0), and build documentation.

By forcing all code additions to pass through pull requests, we ensure that all project additions are traceable and pass our quality control checks. In addition, we have integrated documentation HTML pages generated automatically from source code files, again avoiding duplication of effort. Because of these measures, HADDOCKv3 is becoming a reference repository on effective open-science practices for organising a scientific software repository. These efforts have generated impact on talks and publications (see *D3.7 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (final)*, available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6670331>).

In summary, during BioExcel-2 HADDOCKv3 has fully matured from proof-of-concept to a beta-stable release, already providing users with documentation and examples as well as what we believe are relevant user-enhancing experiences (command-line functionalities).

5 QM/MM – GROMACS & CP2K

The [GROMACS/CP2K QM/MM interface](#) is a new feature introduced in Bioexcel-2. It enables coupling a molecular mechanics description of a system, with a density

functional theory description using two highly parallel codes, GROMACS and [CP2K](#). This is done through the standardised [MDModule](#) interface in GROMACS, which was developed in BioExcel. Another part of the project is improving the absolute and parallel scaling performance of the parts of CP2K that are most relevant for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems.

5.1 Software release

With the new GROMACS/CP2K interface, released with GROMACS 2022 (latest release 2022.1 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451564>), it is now possible to perform scalable high-performance QM/MM simulations of biological systems under periodic boundary conditions.

To improve user experience and usability, topologies are automatically converted from standard MM to QM/MM and default CP2K input parameters sets have been integrated into the grompp tool of GROMACS. While these functionalities target new users, who benefit from a smooth and straightforward setup of their systems for QM/MM simulation, the interface design also allows advanced users to modify most of the individual CP2K parameters for improved performance or for employing non-standard methods.

Our experience supporting new users of the QM/MM interface revealed that installation, in particular building CP2K to create the libcp2k library and linking to this when building GROMACS, often proved problematic. We therefore collaborated with the CP2K core development team, who in response to our request modified CP2K to produce link line information for libcp2k that could automatically be picked up by GROMACS when building it with the QM/MM interface.

Developed QM/MM interface is based on the [MDModule](#) framework of GROMACS, which provides a unified, modularized and maintainable platform for introducing additional (external) forces into an MD simulation. A typical GROMACS *mdrun* simulation workflow for QM/MM simulations with the new MDModule-based CP2K interface is illustrated in **Figure 5**. Interactions with the core *mdrun* functionality as well as requests for receiving data from other GROMACS modules are implemented via the MDModules notifications mechanism. Interaction with CP2K routines is achieved via the *libcp2k* functionality for transferring data and executing QM calculations, which is linked with *mdrun* into a single executable.

Figure 5. GROMACS MD workflow with CP2K QM/MM interface. Interface part is shown in red

There are two main drivers for further developments: (i) expanding scope of scientific questions, which can be treated using QM/MM and (ii) improving usability of the interface based on feedback from users obtained from e.g., forums, e-mail, interviews, conferences, workshops, *etc.* Release of the new features and bug fixes is synchronised with the official GROMACS release schedule.

5.2 User support and issues tracking

An issue tracking system of GROMACS on Gitlab is used to track issues, report bugs and create feature requests (<https://gitlab.com/gromacs/gromacs/-/issues>). In addition, a Bioexcel forum dedicated to QM/MM simulations is used to respond to user requests and problems (ask.bioexcel.eu/c/qmmm-biosim/20). In case of bugs or feature requests, information from the forum is forwarded to the GROMACS Gitlab and processed there in a standardised way with Gitlab issue tracking system.

5.3 Strategies for usage of HPC resources with QM/MM interface

Enhancing the sampling in our QM/MM simulations by means of Umbrella Sampling (US) or AWH is trivially parallel with perfect or near-perfect efficiency. It should be noted that usage of the AWH simulations for calculating free energy profiles associated with the chemical reactions in combination with multiwalker parallelization schemes are particularly suitable for QM/MM description of the system.

5.4 Documentation accompanying release of QM/MM interface

In order to facilitate uptake and productive usage of the GROMACS-CP2K QM/MM interface for biomolecular simulation, we produced documentation that guides users on best practice https://docs.bioexcel.eu/qmmm_bpg (see also Figure 6). Our experience supporting new users of the QM/MM interface revealed that installation, in particular building CP2K to create the libcp2k library and linking

to this when building GROMACS, often proved problematic. We therefore provided build advice in the GROMACS manual: <https://manual.gromacs.org/2022.1/install-guide/index.html#installing-with-cp2k> We also included high level build advice in our best practice guide to help new users navigate the fairly complex CP2K build procedure: https://docs.bioexcel.eu/qmmm_bpg/en/main/running_cp2k/building_cp2k.html

The image shows a screenshot of a web page titled "CP2K QM/MM Best Practice Guide". On the left is a navigation sidebar with sections: OVERVIEW (QM/MM overview), SYSTEM PREPARATION (System preparation, Selecting QM atoms), INPUT PREPARATION (CP2K MM setup, QM treatment, CP2K QM/MM parameterisation), and RUNNING CP2K (Building CP2K, Running QM/MM simulations with CP2K, Understanding the CP2K output, CP2K Troubleshooting). The main content area is titled "QM/MM parameterisation with the GROMACS/CP2K interface" and includes a "View page source" link. The text explains that the chapter describes setting up a QM/MM system within the GROMACS/CP2K interface, assuming an equilibrated GROMACS coordinates file (.gro), a GROMACS topology file (.top), and a MD parameter file (.mdp). It then discusses "Selecting QM atoms", stating that atoms must be given through a GROMACS index file (.ndx) and that a group of atoms can be named (e.g., QMatoms). An example command is shown: `gmx_mpi make_ndx -f ${INPUT}.gro`. Below the command is a terminal output showing the analysis of residue names and atom counts for different groups.

```
gmx_mpi make_ndx -f ${INPUT}.gro

Reading structure file
Going to read 0 old index file(s)
Analysing residue names:
There are: 1 Other residues
There are: 2384 Water residues
Analysing residues not classified as Protein/DNA/RNA/Water and splitting into gro

0 System      : 7186 atoms
1 Other       : 34 atoms
2 Protein     : 34 atoms
```

Figure 6: Best Practice Guide including guidance on usage of GROMACS-CP2K interface

As described in deliverable *D3.7 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (final)* (available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6670331>) we also developed a variety of training materials for QM/MM with GROMACS+CP2K, for example the following, which was used in a training organised together with PRACE and the ARCHER2 HPC service:

<https://www.archer2.ac.uk/training/courses/210422-gromacs>

<https://docs.bioexcel.eu/2021-04-22-qmmm-gromacs-cp2k>

The new CP2K interface was also presented in several webinars:

https://bioexcel.eu/qmmm_interface_webinar

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GqUq8T98gP8>

5.5 Expansion of the BioExcel QM/MM Benchmark Suite

The BioExcel QM/MM benchmark suite (available from https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_suite) had its initial release at project half time as part of deliverable D1.4 (see the D1.4 release of the BioExcel QM/MM Benchmark Suite, available from

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3885124>). For the D1.6 release of the BioExcel QM/MM Benchmark Suite (available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6676034>) the suite has been expanded significantly to include the following additional benchmarks (see also Figure 7):

- Versions of the MQAE (solute-solvent), ClC (ion channel), and CBD_PHY (phytochrome) benchmarks that use the hybrid DFT functionals PBE0 and B3LYP to incorporate Hartree-Fock exchange energy (the initial release of the benchmark suite included only the GGA functionals PBE and BLYP).
- Versions of the MQAE and ClC benchmarks that make use of the Auxiliary Density Matrix Method (ADMM) to markedly reduce the high computational cost of the molecular-environment-optimised MOLOPT basis set when used in combination with hybrid functionals such as B3LYP and PBE0.
- Versions of the MQAE and ClC benchmarks that use the EMSL basis set in combination with the B3LYP hybrid functional.
- A version of the ClC-19 benchmark that uses the HFX basis set in combination with the B3LYP hybrid functional.
- A version of the MQAE benchmark in which the linear size of the cell defining the quantum region is increased by a factor 2, i.e. where the volume of the quantum region is enlarged by a factor 8.

This expansion of the benchmark suite was driven by the need to enable systematic benchmarking and profiling investigation of the performance of CP2K under a more fully representative range of QM treatments for biomolecular systems, especially hybrid functionals. The additional benchmarks were also chosen strategically to be carefully controlled variations on the initial set rather than entirely new systems so as to make it possible through comparison between results for various pairs of benchmarks to discern the effect on performance and parallel scaling of changes in individual key QM treatment parameters like the number of QM atoms, the size of the QM region, and the choice of functional and basis set, with all other parameters being held equal to the extent possible.

Name	Functional	QM cell size	Basis set	QM atoms	Total atoms
MQAE-BLYP	BLYP	14 x 17 x 11	MOLOPT	34	~16k
MQAE-B3LYP-MOLOPT-ADMM	B3LYP				

MQAE-B3LYP			EMSL		
MQAE-B3LYP-large		28 x 34 x 22			
CBD_PHY-PBE	PBE	25 x 25 x 25	MOLOPT	68	~168k
CBD_PHY-PBE0	PBE0		HFX		
CIC-19-BLYP	BLYP	18 x 18 x 18	MOLOPT	19	~150k
CIC-19-B3LYP-MOLOPT-ADMM					
CIC-19-B3LYP	B3LYP		EMSL		
CIC-19-B3LYP-HFXBASIS			HFX		
CIC-19-PBE0	PBE0		EMSL		
CIC-253-BLYP	BLYP	27 x 25 x 25	MOLOPT	253	
CIC-253-B3LYP	B3LYP		EMSL		
CIC-253-PBE0	PBE0				

Figure 7: Expanded BioExcel QM/MM Benchmark Suite, with new additions since the D1.4 release highlighted in green.

5.6 Software to analyse and visualise CP2K parallel performance for QM/MM MD

In order to analyse CP2K parallel performance for biomolecular QM/MM as part of our systematic benchmarking and profiling investigation during the second half

of the project we produced Python code that allows a user to process sets of standard format CP2K output files: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6670413>.

The code extracts data from within CP2K output logs that use an application-defined syntax. It can compute averages over repeated runs, subtract off simulation initialisation costs for MD runs, and compute per-MD-step averages if provided with two runs for identical inputs (except different number of MD steps). The code allows a user to compute per-MD-step averages of the execution walltime and speedup and can compute the fractional contributions of the top n (a user-specified number) most costly CP2K subroutines, as well as the load imbalance across MPI ranks of these subroutines, in a way that enables these metrics to be compared for different core counts in order to discern how different subroutines scale. Finally, the code can generate visualisations of the computed metrics, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Example performance metrics (average execution time per MD step, speedup, parallel scaling of subroutine fractional contributions to execution time, and load imbalances) computed from CP2K output data using our analysis & visualisation code

This analysis code proved crucial for obtaining additional actionable insights into CP2K performance, which guided decisions regarding our CP2K QM/MM optimisation work during the second half of the project.

5.7 Report on CP2K biomolecular benchmarking and performance profiling and sharing of underlying data

The results of our systematic CP2K QM/MM benchmarking and performance profiling for biomolecular systems are summarised in the following report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591574>. Bottlenecks in absolute performance and parallel scaling were found to depend strongly on the QM parametrisation, for example on the density functional, in particular whether a GGA or hybrid functional is used – in the latter case four_center electron repulsion integrals and derivatives computed by the libint library dominated performance. Other factors

affecting which subroutines appear as top contributors to runtime at larger parallel scale include the number of QM atoms and the size of the QM region, with no single subroutine-level bottleneck being an overwhelmingly dominant impediment to performance in all cases. The insights obtained by studying these results guided our CP2K optimisation work during the second half of the project, including the (re)prioritisation of development goals, as reported in the software development roadmap described in deliverable D1.5 – Long-term hardware and application roadmap (available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840262>).

In the interest of reproducibility, in order to clarify the rationale underlying our development decisions, and for potential future reference and further investigation we have made public not only the benchmarks themselves (i.e. the BioExcel QM/MM Benchmark Suite), the summary report, and the code used to generate the figures included in the report, but also the raw CP2K output data from which these were generated: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675865>.

5.8 Plane wave integral optimisations in CP2K v9.1 release

As described in the software roadmap deliverable D1.5, we identified that the fractional contribution to per-MD-step average execution time of the CP2K subroutine *pw_integral_ab*, which computes the integral for two functions in plane wave basis representations, grows to become an important bottleneck to parallel scaling on larger number of cores. This was traced back to calls to high-accuracy Kahan summation of arrays.

In consultation with the CP2K developers we replaced these with a standard sum, only to be called during QM/MM calculations, which we verified had no discernible effect on scientific results (computed energies) despite an in-principle reduction in accuracy, with the new version of the code passing all the same CP2K regression tests as prior to implementation. Finally, we implemented OpenMP optimisation of the standard sum in order to take advantage of multithreaded execution, which our systematic benchmarking showed is often optimal (up to small numbers of threads per rank).

[Our commit with this optimisation](#) was integrated into the official v9.1 (January 2022) release of CP2K. The degree of the resulting performance improvement, which is relevant for GGA functionals such as PBE and BLYP, depends on the biomolecular system and the corecount. As shown in Figure 9, it can easily yield a factor two reduction in the walltime of *pw_integral_ab*.

Figure 9: improved CP2K performance on the MQAE-BLYP benchmark for 8 threads of *pw_integral_ab* after replacement of Kahan sum with standard sum and its OpenMP parallelisation

Availability

Project releases are made available on <https://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories/>. The final release for BioExcel-2 can be found there, and is also available directly from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6761700>.

The individual components - software, documentation, tests, benchmarks and benchmark reports - that make up this D1.6 project release are also archived and available separately on Zenodo:

- GROMACS
 - GROMACS 2022.1 source code <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451564>
 - GROMACS 2022.1 manual <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451567>
 - GROMACS 2021.5 source code (maintenance release) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5850051>
 - GROMACS 2021.5 manual (maintenance release) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5849961>
 - GROMACS 2020.7 source code (maintenance release) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5938877>
 - GROMACS 2020.7 manual (maintenance release) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5938884>
 -
- PMX
 - pmx release June2022 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671368>
- HADDOCK

- HADDOCK v3.0.0-beta.1
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6593819>
- 1st stable release of haddock-pilot
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6593427>
- 3rd stable release of the haddock-tools
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6593626>
- 1st release of benchmark-tools
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6593526>
- QM/MM w/ CP2K
 - Official v9.1 release of CP2K that includes BioExcel contributions reported in D1.6:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6760368>
 - Software to analyse and visualise CP2K parallel MD performance
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6670413>
 - D1.6 release of BioExcel QM/MM Benchmark Suite
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6676034>
 - CP2K biomolecular QM/MM benchmarking data
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6670413>
 - Report on CP2K biomolecular QM/MM performance profiling
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591574>

Binary distributions of BioExcel core applications as Docker containers and Conda packages are described in deliverable [D2.6 – Integration of BioExcel software framework with standards and international initiatives](#).

Releases of the [BioExcel building blocks](#) (BioBB) and WP3 [workflows](#) will be described in deliverable *D2.7 – Final release of demonstration workflows*.